

Computation of the Gamma Function of Half using the Gaussian Integral

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Abstract: The Gaussian integral, also known as the Euler-Poisson integral, is the integral of the Gaussian function over the real line. The integral has wide range application in quantum mechanics, probability and statistics. This paper proves the Gamma function of half ($\frac{1}{2}$) using the Gaussian integral.

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1. Introduction

In general, the factorial [1-6] for positive integer n , denoted by $n!$, is the product of all positive integers less than or equal to n . For example, $5! = 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 4 \times 5 = 720$. Note that $0! = 1$. In this article, the gamma function is proved using the natural logarithm and Pi function, also known as Euler's factorial function, and the gamma function of $\frac{1}{2}$.

2. Natural Logarithm

The natural logarithm of a real or complex number is a technique to solve the exponential function and vice-versa [7-10].

The natural logarithm is defined as follows:

$$\log_e u = \ln u.$$

The properties of natural logarithm are given below:

$$\ln u^v = v \ln u.$$

$$\ln uv = \ln u + \ln v.$$

$$\ln \frac{u}{v} = \ln u - \ln v.$$

$$\ln \frac{1}{u} = \ln 1 - \ln u = -\ln u (\because \ln 1 = 0).$$

$$\ln e = 1.$$

Let $e^m = n$, then $\ln n = m$. Also, $e^{\ln n} = n$ and $\ln e^m = m$.

$$-\ln e^{-r} = -(-r) = r.$$

3. Gamma Function

The gamma function is proved here using Pi function and natural logarithm

The Pi (Π) function is given below:

$$\Pi(x) = x! = x(x-1)(x-2) \cdots 1, \forall x \in W, \quad (1)$$

where W denotes the system of whole numbers.

Euler's factorial function, also known as Pi (Π) function, is the basis for gamma function [11].

Swiss mathematician Leonhard Euler has defined the pi function by integral as follows:

$$\Pi(x) = \int_0^1 (-\ln t)^n dt, \forall n \in \mathbf{W}, \quad (2)$$

where \ln denotes the logarithm to the base of the mathematical constant e .

By substituting $t = e^{-x}$; $dt = -e^{-x}dx$; $t = 0 \Rightarrow e^{-x} = 0 \Rightarrow x = \infty$ and $t = 1 \Rightarrow e^{-x} = 1 \Rightarrow x = 0$ in (2), we obtain

$$\Pi(x) = \int_{\infty}^0 -x^n e^{-x} dx = \int_0^{\infty} x^n e^{-x} dx, \quad \forall n \in \mathbf{W}, \quad (3)$$

where $(-\ln t)^n = (-\ln e^{-x})^n = (-(-x))^n = x^n$.

By integrating (3), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &= [-x^n e^{-x}]_0^{\infty} - \int_0^{\infty} -nx^{n-1} e^{-x} dx. \\ &= [x^{\infty} e^{-\infty} - 0] - \int_0^{\infty} -nx^{n-1} e^{-x} dx. \end{aligned}$$

Here, $x^{\infty} e^{-\infty}$ is in indeterminate form. Let us apply L'Hospital's rule,

$$\begin{aligned} i. e. \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x^n}{e^x} &= \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{nx^{n-1}}{e^x} = \dots = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n(n-1) \dots 1}{e^x} = 0. \\ &= 0 - \int_0^{\infty} -nx^{n-1} e^{-x} dx. \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Now, } \Pi(x) = n \int_0^{\infty} x^{n-1} e^{-x} dx. \quad (4)$$

By substituting (3) in (4), we obtain

$$\Pi(x) = n\Pi(x-1). \quad (5)$$

The gamma function $\Gamma(x)$ is obtained as follows.

$$\Pi(x) = n\Pi(x-1) \Rightarrow \Gamma(x+1) = n\Gamma(x). \quad (6)$$

$$n\Gamma(x) = n \int_0^{\infty} x^{n-1} e^{-x} dx \Rightarrow \Gamma(x) = \int_0^{\infty} x^{n-1} e^{-x} dx. \quad (7)$$

The gamma function [7-8], therefore, is derived from the Euler's factorial function (Pi function) that uses the actual factorial function.

4. The Gaussian Integral

The Gaussian integral is the integral of the Gaussian function $f(x) = e^{-x^2}$ over the real line is shown below:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} dx = \sqrt{\pi}.$$

Proof. Let $I = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} dx = 2 \int_0^{\infty} e^{-x^2} dx = 2 \int_0^{\infty} e^{-y^2} dy$

$$I^2 = 2 \int_0^{\infty} e^{-x^2} dx \times 2 \int_0^{\infty} e^{-y^2} dy = 4 \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-(x^2+y^2)} dx dy$$

Let $y^2 = (xt)^2 \Rightarrow y = xt \Rightarrow t = \frac{y}{x}; dy = x dt. y = 0 \Rightarrow t = 0, y = \infty \Rightarrow t = \infty.$

$$4 \int_{t=0}^{t=\infty} \int_{x=0}^{x=\infty} e^{-(x^2+x^2t^2)} dx(xdt) = \int_{t=0}^{t=\infty} \int_{x=0}^{x=\infty} xe^{-x^2(1+t^2)} dx dt$$

Let $u = x^2(1+t^2); \frac{1}{2(1+t^2)} du = x dx; x = 0 \Rightarrow u = 0; x = \infty \Rightarrow u = \infty.$

$$4 \int_{t=0}^{t=\infty} \frac{1}{2(1+t^2)} \int_{u=0}^{u=\infty} e^{-u} du dt = 4 \int_{t=0}^{t=\infty} \frac{1}{2(1+t^2)} \left[\frac{e^{-u}}{-1} \right]_0^{\infty} dt = 4 \int_{t=0}^{t=\infty} \frac{1}{2(1+t^2)} dt$$

Here, $\left[\frac{e^{-u}}{-1} \right]_0^{\infty} = -(e^{-\infty} - e^0) = -(0 - 1) = 1.$

$$4 \int_{t=0}^{t=\infty} \frac{1}{2(1+t^2)} dt = 2 \int_{t=0}^{t=\infty} \frac{1}{(1+t^2)} dt = 2[\tan^{-1} t]_0^{\infty} = 2(\tan^{-1} \infty - \tan^{-1} 0)$$

$$I^2 = 2(\tan^{-1} \infty - \tan^{-1} 0) = 2\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - 0\right) = \pi \Rightarrow I = \sqrt{\pi}. \left(\because I = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} dx \right)$$

From the above equation, we conclude that

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} dx = \sqrt{\pi}.$$

Hence, Proved.

5. Computation of $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$

Gamma Function: $\Gamma(t) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{n-1} e^{-t} dt$

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{\frac{1}{2}-1} e^{-t} dt = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-t}}{\sqrt{t}} dt = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} \frac{dt}{\sqrt{t}}$$

Let $y = \sqrt{t} \Rightarrow y^2 = t; 2y dy = dt \Rightarrow 2dy = \frac{dt}{y} = \frac{dt}{\sqrt{t}}$

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} \frac{dt}{\sqrt{t}} = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-y^2} (2dy) = 2 \int_0^{\infty} e^{-y^2}$$

The Gaussian Integral indicates that $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-x^2} dx = 2 \int_0^{\infty} e^{-x^2} dx = \sqrt{\pi}.$

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{\frac{1}{2}-1} e^{-t} dt = 2 \int_0^{\infty} e^{-y^2} = \sqrt{\pi}.$$

Therefore, $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\pi}.$

6. Conclusion

In this article, The Gamma function of $\frac{1}{2}$ has been proved using the Gaussian integral. This idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

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